

KnowledgePanel®

**Ipsos Public Affairs
Project Report for the
Social Connection in America – 2025**

Submitted to:
Steven Crane, MS, Stanford University

Date Revised Report Submitted: May 20, 2025

Ipsos Project Director: Abigail Giles
Ipsos Account Executive: Wendy Mansfield
Ipsos Job Number: 25-027530-01

Table of Contents

STUDY DESIGN & DOCUMENTATION	3
INTRODUCTION	3
SAMPLE DEFINITION, FIELD PERIOD AND SURVEY LENGTH	3
DATA PROCESSING TO ENSURE DATA QUALITY.....	4
LIMITATIONS OF THE DESIGN AND DATA COLLECTION	4
SURVEY COOPERATION ENHANCEMENTS.....	4
DATA FILE DELIVERABLES AND DESCRIPTIONS	4
KEY PERSONNEL.....	7
IPSOS KNOWLEDGEPANEL® METHODOLOGY	8
INTRODUCTION	8
IPSOS PUBLIC AFFAIRS.....	9
KNOWLEDGEPANEL METHODOLOGY	9
KNOWLEDGEPANEL LATINO SM RECRUITMENT	10
HOUSEHOLD MEMBER RECRUITMENT	10
SURVEY SAMPLING FROM KNOWLEDGEPANEL.....	10
SURVEY ADMINISTRATION.....	11
RESPONSE RATES	12
IPSOS KNOWLEDGEPANEL WEIGHTING	12
STUDY-SPECIFIC POST-STRATIFICATION WEIGHTS.....	12
TRIMMING.....	13
DESIGN EFFECT AND MARGIN OF SAMPLING ERROR.....	13
RANGE ON WEIGHTS.....	13
APPENDIX A: WEIGHTING BENCHMARK DISTRIBUTIONS.....	15

Survey items, their sourcing, and copyright information provided in the appendix of the 2025 *Social Connection in America™* Report. See <https://socialconnectioninamerica.org>

Suggested Citation:

Holt-Lunstad J, Bruss K, Crane SM, Ishayik E. *Social Connection in America™*. Barnes Family Foundation; 2025. doi:10.5281/zenodo.17410026

Study Design & Documentation

Introduction

Ipsos Public Affairs (Ipsos) conducted the Social Connection in America – 2025 survey on behalf of The Barnes Family Foundation.

This study establishes the premier annual measure for social connection in the U.S. It will be an annual, nationally representative, probability-based, cross-sectional survey conducted over twenty-five (25) years, covering individual-level connection, with plans for future years to cover community-level connection.

Specific objectives are as follows:

- Set the authoritative definitions and measures both for individual- and community-level connection for a national level;
- Collect data with a consistent set of measures to set nationwide benchmarks;
- Reliably track trends in social connection across years correlated with health and societal outcomes;
- Raise awareness about the impact of social connection on health;
- Provide policymakers and practitioners data they need to advocate for structural changes that promote social connection; and,
- Plant a flag and create momentum, drawing in partners and funders to invest in, and build on our product.

Sample Definition, Field Period and Survey Length

The survey was conducted on KnowledgePanel®, the largest online panel in the United States that relies on probability-based sampling methods for recruitment to provide a representative sampling frame for adults ages 18 and older residing in the United States. The sampling method was designed to provide national and modeled state estimates.

Ipsos invited one adult from a representative sample of households to partake in this survey. Selected panel members received an email invitation to complete the survey and were asked to do so at their earliest convenience.

The survey was administered to both English and Spanish survey-takers and consisted of two stages: A pretest followed by a main survey. The main survey sample release consisted of a soft launch followed by a full launch.

The median completion time of the main survey was 5 minutes.

The completion and qualification rates for the pretest and main surveys are presented below.

	Field Start	Field End	N Fielded	N Completed	Completion Rate	N Qualified	Qualification Rate
Pretest	04/23/2025	04/25/25	83	33	40%	33	100%
Main	04/29/2025	05/13/25	15,121	10,107	67%	10,107*	100%

*Of the 10,107 cases completing the main survey, n=83 were cleaned out by Ipsos, with 10,024 being delivered to the client (excluding speeders and constant refusers) to be included in the final analyses.

Data Processing to Ensure Data Quality

Respondents are unable to complete the survey more than once; after completing the survey one time, respondents no longer have access to the survey.

Limitations of the Design and Data Collection

All forms of public opinion research are subject to unmeasured error that cannot be eliminated. When a probability-based panel like KnowledgePanel is used, Ipsos employs the total survey error approach to identify and minimize error due to coverage error, sampling error, nonresponse error, measurement error, and data processing and editing error. Coverage error is addressed in our KnowledgePanel recruitment strategies. Sampling error is addressed in recruitment and at the time of sample selection for each study. Nonresponse error is reduced in recruitment, study sampling, panel management strategies (including communication, incentive, and retention protocols), and weighting of the final data. These strategies support the computation of sampling error to estimate the extent to which the results from the sample might differ from population values. To reduce measurement error, our research staff evaluates questionnaires in terms of item flow, wording, and response formats to provide respondent-friendly surveys and elicit high-quality data. Additionally, we conduct a quality control review of data processing steps and any data cleaning to minimize errors.

Survey Cooperation Enhancements

As standard with KnowledgePanel surveys, email reminders were sent to non-responders on Day 3 of the field period. An additional reminder was sent to the remaining non-responders on Day 7 and 10 of the field period.

Data File Deliverables and Descriptions

For each survey, Ipsos prepared and delivered fully-formatted SPSS and .CSV datasets containing the survey and demographic data with the appropriate variable and value labels. The table below shows the final Pretest and Main survey files delivered:

Delivery Date	File Type	File Name	N Records
4/25/2025	SPSS/CSV	Social Connection Pretest Client_04252025.sav	33
5/20/2025	SPSS/CSV	26794_Social Connection Main_Weighted Client_Replicate1_05202025	1,000

*Per client's request, Ipsos delivered a random and balanced sample of 1,000 cases to be followed by a second delivery of 1,000 cases, followed by the remaining qualified completes.

In addition, Ipsos prepared and delivered other deliverables as follows:

- Post-stratification statistical weights
- Item timing data in seconds for all respondents
- Demographic profile data for all assigned sample
- Additional non-demographic profile data for all qualified respondents

In addition to the survey variables from the Main interview, Ipsos' standard demographic profile variables and a series of data processing variables created by Ipsos were provided in the data file. The following table shows the name and description of all variables included in the Main survey dataset.

	Label
CaseID	Case ID
qflag	Qualification Flag
tm_start	Interview start time (GMT)
tm_finish	Interview finish time (GMT)
duration	Interview duration in minutes
weight	Post-stratification weight (without political party adjustment)
ppage	Age
ppeduc5	Education (5 Categories)
ppeducat	Education (4 Categories)
ppethm	Race / Ethnicity
ppgender	Gender
pphhsiz	Household Size
pphouse4	Housing Type
ppinc7	Household Income

ppmarit5	Marital Status
ppmsacat	MSA Status
ppreg4	Region 4 - Based on State of Residence
pprent	Ownership Status of Living Quarters
ppstaten	State
ppemploy	Current Employment Status
ppkid017	Presence of Household Members - Children 0-17
ppt18ov	Presence of Household Members - Adults 18+
ppreg9	Region 9 - Based on State of residence
xspanish	Survey Language
xacslang	Language Proficiency
xppracem	Race
xhispan	Hispanic Origin
xpph1bmi	DERIVED: Body mass index (BMI)
ppcm0040	Q10: Which, if any, of the following pets do you have? [DO NOT HAVE ANY PETS]
pph1diab	Q19: Have YOU been diagnosed by a doctor or other qualified medical professional with any of the following medical conditions? [Diabetes or pre-diabetes]
pph1hatk	Q19: Have YOU been diagnosed by a doctor or other qualified medical professional with any of the following medical conditions? [Heart attack, heart disease, or other heart condition]
pph1hype	Q19: Have YOU been diagnosed by a doctor or other qualified medical professional with any of the following medical conditions? [High blood pressure or hypertension]
pph1inso	Q19: Have YOU been diagnosed by a doctor or other qualified medical professional with any of the following medical conditions? [Sleep disorders such as sleep apnea or insomnia]
pph1stro	Q19: Have YOU been diagnosed by a doctor or other qualified medical professional with any of the following medical conditions? [Stroke]
pph1anxi	Q19a: Have YOU been diagnosed with any of the following mental health conditions [Anxiety disorder]
Extraversion	BFI Extraversion scale score
pph12006	Q190: Because of a physical, mental, or emotional condition, do you having difficulty running errands such as visiting a doctor's office or shopping?
pppagnid	DERIVED: Gender identification
pppa_lgb	Q230: Which of the following best describes how you think of yourself?
ppp10012	Q11: In general, do you think of yourself as...

pph11726	Q35A: How often do you do VIGOROUS leisure-time physical activities for AT LEAST 10 Minutes that cause HEAVY sweating or LARGE increases in breathing or heart rate?
pph11727	Q35B: How often do you do LIGHT OR MODERATE leisure-time physical activities for AT LEAST 10 MINUTES that cause ONLY LIGHT sweating or a SLIGHT to MODERATE increase in breathing or heart rate?
ppsi2302	Q60: How many minutes did it usually take you to get to work LAST WEEK?
ppcp0005	Q150: In a typical week, about how many hours do you spend on the internet for personal use?
ppc21531	CU410: How often do you use the following websites and online services? [Facebook]
ppc21535	CU410: How often do you use the following websites and online services? [YouTube]
ppc21549	CU410: How often do you use the following websites and online services? [Instagram]
ppc21911	CU410: How often do you use the following websites and online services? [TikTok]
pph11413	Q24_1: Are you a caregiver for an adult family member or friend?
ppracem	Race, Census categories
ppm22203	Q4: In a typical week (Monday - Sunday), approximately how many hours do you spend watching TV shows or movies?

Key Personnel

Key personnel on the study include:

Wendy Mansfield – Senior Vice President, Research Development. W. Mansfield is based in Washington, DC.

Email: wendy.mansfield@ipsos.com

Jared Coopersmith – Vice President, Chief Statistician. J. Coopersmith is based in Baltimore, MD.

Email: Jared.Coopersmith@ipsos.com

Brittany Alexander – Statistician, Data Analytics and Applied Sciences Group. B. Alexander is based in Washington, DC.

Email: brittany.alexander@ipsos.com

Elisa Chan – Vice President, Data Analytics and Applied Sciences. E. Chan is based in Sunnyvale, CA.

Email: elisa.chan@ipsos.com

Leticia Maciel - Director, Data Analytics and Applied Sciences. L. Maciel is based in Sunnyvale, CA.

Email: leticia.maciel@ipsos.com

Abigail Giles – Director, Public Affairs. A. Giles is based in Seattle, WA.

Email: abigail.giles@ipsos.com

Ipsos KnowledgePanel® Methodology

Introduction

Ipsos is passionate about social science, health, and public policy research. We collaborate closely with our clients throughout the research process, while applying rigor in every step. We specialize in innovative online research that consistently gives leaders in academia, government, and business the confidence to make important decisions. Ipsos delivers affordable, statistically valid online research through KnowledgePanel® and leverages a variety of other assets, such as world-class advanced analytics, an industry-leading physician panel, an innovative platform for measuring online ad effectiveness, and a research-ready behavioral database of frequent supermarket and drug store shoppers.

KnowledgePanel is the first and largest online research panel that is representative of the entire U.S. population. Panel members are randomly recruited through probability-based sampling, and households are provided with access to the Internet and hardware if needed.

Ipsos recruits panel members using address-based sampling (ABS) methods to ensure full coverage of all households in the nation. Once household members are recruited for the panel and assigned to a study sample, they are notified by email for survey taking, or panelists can visit their online member page for survey taking (instead of being contacted by telephone or postal mail). This allows surveys to be fielded quickly and economically. In addition, this approach reduces the burden placed on respondents, since email notification is less intrusive than telephone calls and the self-administered mode minimizes social desirability bias and positivity effects that can be present with an interviewer. Many respondents find answering online questionnaires more interesting and engaging than being questioned by a telephone interviewer. Furthermore, respondents have the convenience to choose what day and time to complete their assigned survey.

Ipsos Public Affairs

Ipsos Public Affairs has a strong tradition in working with sophisticated academic, government, and commercial researchers to provide high quality research, samples, and analyses. The larger Ipsos offers the fundamental knowledge governmental agencies, academics, industries, retailers, services companies and the media need to provide exceptional quality in research to make effective decisions. It delivers a comprehensive range of information and consultancy services. Ipsos is one of the leading survey research organizations worldwide, operating in 90 countries with over 16,000 employees.

For further information, visit our website: www.ipsos.com.

KnowledgePanel Methodology

KnowledgePanel provides probability-based samples with an “organic” representation of the study population for measurement of public opinions, attitudes, and behaviors. The panel was first developed in 1999 by Knowledge Networks, an Ipsos company. Panel members are randomly selected so that survey results can properly represent the U.S. population with a measurable level of accuracy and a calculable response rate, features that are not obtainable from nonprobability or opt-in online panels (for comparisons of results from probability versus nonprobability methods, see MaInnis et al., 2018¹ and Yeager et al., 2011²).

KnowledgePanel’s recruitment process was originally based exclusively on a national RDD sampling methodology. In 2009, in light of the growing proportion of cellphone-only households, Ipsos migrated to an ABS recruitment methodology via the U.S. Postal Service’s Delivery Sequence File (DSF)³. ABS not only improves population coverage, but also provides a more effective means for recruiting hard-to-reach individuals, such as cellphone-only households, non-internet households, young adults, and persons of color. Households without an internet connection are provided with a web-enabled device and free internet service.

After initially accepting the invitation to join the panel, participants are asked to complete a short demographic survey (the initial Core Profile Survey); answers to this survey allow efficient panel sampling and weighting for future surveys. Upon completing the Core Profile Survey, participants become active panel members. All panel members are provided privacy and confidentiality protections.

Adults from sampled households are invited to join KnowledgePanel through a series of mailings, including an initial invitation letter, a reminder postcard, and a subsequent follow-up letter. Moreover, telephone refusal-conversion calls are made to nonresponding households for

¹ MaInnis, B., Krosnick, J., Ho, A., and M. Cho (2018). “The Accuracy of Measurements with Probability and Nonprobability Survey Samples: Replication and Extension.” *Public Opinion Quarterly*, Winter 2018.

² Yeager, D., Krosnick, J., Chang, L., Javitz, H., Levendusky, M., Simper, A. and R. Wang (2011). “Comparing the Accuracy of RDD Telephone Surveys and Internet Surveys Conducted With Probability and Non-Probability Samples.” *Public Opinion Quarterly*, Winter 2011.

³ Fahimi, M. and D. Kulp (2009). “Address-Based Sampling – Alternatives for Surveys That Require Contacts with Representative Samples of Households.” *Quirk’s Marketing Research Review*, May 2009.

which a telephone number could be matched to a physical address. Invited households can join the panel by:

- Completing and mailing back a paper form in a postage-paid envelope
- Calling a toll-free hotline phone number maintained by Ipsos
- Going to a designated Ipsos website and completing the recruitment form online

KnowledgePanel LatinoSM Recruitment

In 2008, KnowledgePanel LatinoSM was developed to provide researchers with the capability to conduct representative online surveys with United States Hispanics, including both English and Spanish-dominant Hispanics. With the advent of KnowledgePanel Latino, the first United States online panel representative of Hispanics was established to include those without Internet access and those who only speak Spanish. Hispanic members recruited through our traditional ABS sampling methodology described above are supplemented with recruitment using a custom dual-frame RDD sampling methodology targeting telephone exchanges associated with census blocks that have a 65% or greater Latino population density (this density level covers just over 50% of the United States Hispanic population). Moreover, cellular numbers from rates centers with high concentration of Hispanics are also used to improve the representation of samples. With this telephone recruitment, households are screened in the Spanish language to only recruit those homes where Spanish is spoken at least half the time.

Household Member Recruitment

During the initial recruitment survey, all household members are enumerated. Following enumeration, attempts are made to recruit every household member who is at least 13 years old to participate in KnowledgePanel surveys. For household members aged 13 to 17, consent is collected from the parents or the legal guardian during the initial recruitment interview. No direct communication with teenagers is attempted before obtaining parental consent.

Survey Sampling from KnowledgePanel

Once panel members are recruited and profiled by completing our Core Profile Survey, they become eligible for selection for client surveys. Typically, specific survey samples are based on an equal probability selection method (EPSEM) for general population surveys. Customized stratified random sampling based on “profile” data can also be implemented as required by the study design. Profile data can also be used when a survey calls for pre-screening—that is, members are drawn from a subsample of the panel, such as females, Republicans, grocery shoppers, etc. (This can reduce screening costs, particularly for lower incidence subgroups.) In such cases, we ensure that all subsequent survey samples drawn that week are selected in such a way as to result in a sample that remains representative of the population distributions.

As detailed above, significant resources and infrastructure are devoted to the recruitment process for KnowledgePanel so that our active panel members can properly represent the adult population of the U.S. This representation is achieved not only with respect to a broad set of geodemographic indicators, but also for hard-to-reach adults (such as those without Internet access or Spanish-language-dominant Hispanics) who are recruited in proper proportions.

Consequently, the raw distribution of KnowledgePanel mirrors that of the U.S. adults fairly closely, barring occasional disparities that emerge for certain subgroups due to differential recruitment and attrition.

For selection of general population samples from KnowledgePanel, a patented methodology has been developed such that samples from the panel behave as EPSEM samples. Briefly, this methodology starts by weighting the pool of active members to the geodemographic benchmarks secured from a combination of the U.S. Census Bureau's American Community Survey (ACS) and the latest March supplement of the U.S. Census Bureau's Current Population Survey (CPS) along several dimensions. Typically, the geodemographic dimensions used for weighting the entire KnowledgePanel include the following dimensions, with additional nesting of dimensions as well:

- Gender (Male/Female)
- Age (18–29, 30–44, 45–59, and 60+)
- Race/Hispanic ethnicity (White/Non-Hispanic, Black/Non-Hispanic, Other or 2+ Races/Non-Hispanic, Hispanic)
- Education (Less than High School, High School, Some College, Bachelor and beyond)
- Census Region (Northeast, Midwest, South, West)
- Household income (under \$10k, \$10K to <\$25k, \$25K to <\$50k, \$50K to <\$75k, \$75K to <\$100k, \$100K to <\$150k, and \$150K+)
- Home ownership status (Own, Rent/Other)
- Household size (1, 2, 3, 4+)
- Metropolitan Area (Yes, No)
- Hispanic Origin (Mexican, Puerto Rican, Cuban, Other, Non-Hispanic)
- Language Dominance (non-Hispanic and English Dominant, Bilingual, and Spanish Dominant Hispanic) when survey is administered in both English and Spanish

Using the resulting weights as measures of size, a probability-proportional-to-size (PPS) procedure is used to select study specific samples. It is the application of this PPS methodology with the imposed size measures that produces demographically balanced and representative samples that behave as EPSEM. Moreover, in instances where a study design requires any form of oversampling of certain subgroups, such departures from an EPSEM design are accounted for by adjusting the design weights in reference to the Census benchmarks for the population of interest.

Survey Administration

Once assigned to a survey, members receive a notification email letting them know there is a new survey available for them to complete. This email notification contains a link that sends them to the survey. No login name or password is required. The field period depends on the client's needs and can range anywhere from a few hours to several weeks.

Typically, after three days, automatic email reminders are sent to all non-responding panel members in the sample. Additional email reminders are sent and custom reminder schedules are set up as needed. To assist panel members with their survey taking, each individual has a personalized member portal listing all assigned surveys that have yet to be completed.

Ipsos also operates an ongoing modest incentive program to encourage participation and create member loyalty. The incentive program includes special raffles and sweepstakes with both cash rewards and other prizes to be won. On average, panel members complete three to four surveys per month with durations of about 10 to 15 minutes per survey. An additional incentive is usually provided for longer surveys.

Response Rates

As a member of the American Association of Public Opinion Research (AAPOR), Ipsos follows the AAPOR standards for response rate reporting. While the AAPOR standards were established for single survey administrations and not for multi-stage panel surveys, we use the Callegaro-DiSogra (2008)⁴ algorithms for calculating KnowledgePanel survey response rates.

Ipsos KnowledgePanel Weighting

Study-Specific Post-Stratification Weights

Once all survey data have been collected and processed, design weights are adjusted to account for any differential nonresponse that may have occurred. Depending on the specific target population for a given study, geodemographic distributions for the corresponding population are obtained from the CPS, the U.S. Census Bureau's American Community Survey (ACS), or in certain instances from the weighted KnowledgePanel profile data. For this purpose, an iterative proportional fitting (raking) procedure is used to produce the final weights. In the final step, calculated weights are examined to identify and, if necessary, trim outliers at the extreme upper and lower tails of the weight distribution. The resulting weights are then scaled to aggregate to the total sample size of all eligible respondents.

For this study, our weighting process included the following steps:

Step 1. In the first step, design weights for KnowledgePanel (KP) assignees were computed to reflect their selection probabilities.

Step 2. The above design weights for KP respondents were weighted to the following geodemographic distributions of the 18 and over US population with finer adjustments within household size (1, 2, 3, 4+) using an iterative proportional fitting (raking) procedure. The needed benchmarks were obtained from the 2024 March Supplement of the Current Population Survey (CPS), except language dominance within Hispanics, which is not available from CPS, was obtained from the 2023 American Community Survey (ACS).

⁴ Callegaro, M. and C. DiSogra (2008). "Computing Response Metrics for Online Panels." *Public Opinion Quarterly*, Vol. 72, No. 5.

- a) Gender (Male, Female) by Age (18-29, 30-44, 45-59, 60+) by Household Size (1, 2, 3, 4+)
- b) Race-Ethnicity (Non-Hispanic White, Non-Hispanic Black, Non-Hispanic Other, Hispanic, Non-Hispanic 2+ Races) by Household Size (1, 2, 3, 4+)
- c) Census Division (New England, Mid-Atlantic, East-North Central, West-North Central, South Atlantic, East-South Central, West-South Central, Mountain, Pacific) by Household Size (1, 2, 3, 4+)
- d) Metropolitan Status (Metro, Non-Metro) by Household Size (1, 2, 3, 4+)
- e) Education (Less than High School, High School, Some College, Bachelor or higher) by Household Size (1, 2, 3, 4+)
- f) Household Income (Under \$25K, \$25K-\$49,999, \$50K-\$74,999, \$75K-\$99,999, \$100K-\$149,999, \$150K and over) by Household Size (1, 2, 3, 4+)
- g) Language Dominance within Hispanic (English Dominant Hispanic, Bilingual Hispanic, Spanish Dominant Hispanic, Non-Hispanic) by Household Size (1, 2, 3, 4+)

Step 3. In the final step, the resulting weights were trimmed and scaled to add up to the total number of respondents. The final weights were labeled as **weight** with 10,024 cases.

Trimming

Household Size 1: None

Household Size 2: None

Household Size 3: (0.11%, 99.89%)

Household Size 4+: (0.55%, 99.45%)

Design Effect and Margin of Sampling Error⁵

Technically a margin of sampling error (MOSE) is survey- and estimate-specific. It is affected by the survey estimate (point estimate, proportion, mean, etc.), the number of cases, and the unequal weighting effect (often called a design effect). Here we provide the MOSE at the 95% confidence level for a point estimate equal to 50% (when the MOSE is at its widest) and when all respondents are accounted for.

Range on Weights

Analysis Variable : weight										
N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Median	Coeff of Variation	1st Pctl	99th Pctl	Sum	Design Effect	MOE (95% level)
10024	0.147	4.898	1	0.852	57.758	0.262	3.19	10024	1.3336	1.13%

⁵ Margin of error is inclusive of the design effect.

Analysis Variable : weight												
hysize4	N Obs	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Median	Coeff of Variation	1st Pctl	99th Pctl	Sum	Design Effect	MOE (95% level)
HH Size 1	1735	1735	0.147	3.074	0.858	0.811	50.947	0.239	2.178	1488.369	1.2596	2.64%
HH Size 2	4148	4148	0.189	3.757	0.843	0.748	43.486	0.262	2.325	3496.528	1.1891	1.66%
HH Size 3	1779	1779	0.247	4.776	1.082	0.937	53.504	0.319	3.328	1924.038	1.2863	2.64%
HH Size 4+	2362	2362	0.234	4.898	1.319	1.123	59.842	0.254	4.371	3115.065	1.3581	2.35%

Detailed information on the demographic distributions of the benchmarks can be found in Appendix A.

Appendix A: Weighting Benchmark Distributions

18+ US Population Benchmarks
Source: March 2024 CPS Supplement Data

Gender	HH Size				Total
	HH Size 1	HH Size 2	HH Size 3	HH Size 4+	
Male	45.53	49.19	49.65	49.57	48.85
Female	54.47	50.81	50.35	50.43	51.15
Total	3.85E+07	9.03E+07	4.98E+07	8.08E+07	2.59E+08

Age	HH Size				Total
	HH Size 1	HH Size 2	HH Size 3	HH Size 4+	
18-29	10.56	14.31	25.16	27.13	19.83
30-44	17.44	17.32	28.67	38.3	26.05
45-59	18.85	21.17	27.57	24.76	23.17
60+	53.14	47.2	18.6	9.81	30.94
Total	3.85E+07	9.03E+07	4.98E+07	8.08E+07	2.59E+08

Age by Gender	HH Size				Total
	HH Size 1	HH Size 2	HH Size 3	HH Size 4+	
18-29 Male	5.67	6.8	13.1	13.78	10.02
18-29 Female	4.89	7.51	12.06	13.35	9.81
30-44 Male	10.46	9.13	14.16	17.97	13.05
30-44 Female	6.98	8.19	14.51	20.33	13.01
45-59 Male	9.7	9.69	13.34	13.09	11.45
45-59 Female	9.15	11.48	14.23	11.67	11.72
60+ Male	19.7	23.57	9.05	4.74	14.34
60+ Female	33.45	23.64	9.55	5.07	16.6
Total	3.85E+07	9.03E+07	4.98E+07	8.08E+07	2.59E+08

Race / Ethnicity	HH Size				Total
	HH Size 1	HH Size 2	HH Size 3	HH Size 4+	
White, Non-Hispanic	66.39	70.49	56.63	49.75	60.76
Black, Non-Hispanic	16.99	9.95	12.89	11.63	12.08
Other, Non-Hispanic	4.78	6.19	8.61	10.02	7.64
Hispanic	10.11	11.99	20	26.84	17.88
2+ Race, Non-Hispanic	1.73	1.37	1.87	1.76	1.64
Total	3.85E+07	9.03E+07	4.98E+07	8.08E+07	2.59E+08

HH Size					
Region (4 category)	hhsizes4				
	HH Size 1	HH Size 2	HH Size 3	HH Size 4+	Total
Northeast	18.08	16.92	16.69	17.4	17.2
Midwest	23.44	21.01	19.36	19.09	20.46
South	38.11	40.14	39.5	36.85	38.69
West	20.38	21.94	24.45	26.65	23.66
Total	3.85E+07	9.03E+07	4.98E+07	8.08E+07	2.59E+08

HH Size					
Region (9 category)	HH Size				
	HH Size 1	HH Size 2	HH Size 3	HH Size 4+	Total
New England	4.87	4.76	4.9	4.28	4.65
Mid-Atlantic	13.21	12.16	11.8	13.12	12.54
East-North Central	16.38	14.04	13.81	13.05	14.03
West-North Central	7.07	6.96	5.55	6.05	6.42
South Atlantic	20.75	21.93	20.99	19.21	20.73
East-South Central	6.34	6.34	5.67	5.07	5.82
West-South Central	11.02	11.87	12.84	12.57	12.15
Mountain	7.29	7.87	7.64	7.52	7.63
Pacific	13.09	14.07	16.81	19.13	16.03
Total	3.85E+07	9.03E+07	4.98E+07	8.08E+07	2.59E+08

HH Size					
MSA	HH Size				
	HH Size 1	HH Size 2	HH Size 3	HH Size 4+	Total
Non-Metro	14.32	15.18	11.74	11.73	13.32
Metro	85.68	84.82	88.26	88.27	86.68
Total	3.85E+07	9.03E+07	4.98E+07	8.08E+07	2.59E+08

HH Size					
Education	HH Size				
	HH Size 1	HH Size 2	HH Size 3	HH Size 4+	Total
Less than HS	8	6.57	8.97	13.06	9.26
HS	27.47	27.96	29.19	29.68	28.66
Some college	27.8	25.63	27.13	25.8	26.29
Bachelor or higher	36.73	39.84	34.71	31.47	35.79
Total	3.85E+07	9.03E+07	4.98E+07	8.08E+07	2.59E+08

HH Size					
HH Income	HH Size				
	HH Size 1	HH Size 2	HH Size 3	HH Size 4+	Total
Under \$25,000	30.67	8.44	5.43	4.07	9.8
\$25,000-\$49,999	26.6	15.45	10.7	9.38	14.3
\$50,000-\$74,999	18.02	16.77	13.81	11.4	14.71
\$75,000-\$99,999	9.82	14.04	12.76	11.98	12.52
\$100,000-\$149,999	8.43	19.78	22.2	22.09	19.28

\$150,000 and over	6.46	25.52	35.09	41.08	29.38
Total	3.85E+07	9.03E+07	4.98E+07	8.08E+07	2.59E+08

State	Frequency	Percent
AK	539420.7	0.21
AL	3896465	1.5
AR	2325576	0.9
AZ	5631891	2.17
CA	30297253	11.68
CO	4683825	1.81
CT	2882456	1.11
DC	548523.6	0.21
DE	816950.4	0.31
FL	18214394	7.02
GA	8527180	3.29
HI	1114235	0.43
IA	2469402	0.95
ID	1489678	0.57
IL	9873596	3.81
IN	5253856	2.03
KS	2213560	0.85
KY	3452621	1.33
LA	3441969	1.33
MA	5538207	2.14
MD	4860602	1.87
ME	1154132	0.44
MI	7813072	3.01
MN	4502242	1.74
MO	4720053	1.82
MS	2233658	0.86
MT	897486.2	0.35
NC	8450402	3.26
ND	597634.9	0.23
NE	1481024	0.57
NH	1119002	0.43
NJ	7270378	2.8
NM	1625475	0.63
NV	2543585	0.98
NY	15312186	5.9
OH	8974869	3.46
OK	3001918	1.16
OR	3414151	1.32
PA	9953134	3.84
RI	858244.5	0.33
SC	4192845	1.62
SD	675137.3	0.26
TN	5501874	2.12
TX	22738267	8.77
UT	2479732	0.96
VA	6751051	2.6

VT	521218.9	0.2
WA	6208380	2.39
WI	4485736	1.73
WV	1395347	0.54
WY	437685	0.17

Source: ACS 2023 Data

Language Proficiency	percent
HH Size 1 English Dominant Hispanic	0.55
HH Size 1 Bilingual Hispanic	0.72
HH Size 1 Spanish Dominant Hispanic	0.22
HH Size 1 Non-Hispanic	13.33
HH Size 2 English Dominant Hispanic	1.43
HH Size 2 Bilingual Hispanic	2.08
HH Size 2 Spanish Dominant Hispanic	0.67
HH Size 2 Non-Hispanic	30.65
HH Size 3 English Dominant Hispanic	1.1
HH Size 3 Bilingual Hispanic	2
HH Size 3 Spanish Dominant Hispanic	0.74
HH Size 3 Non-Hispanic	15.34
HH Size 4 English Dominant Hispanic	1.91
HH Size 4 Bilingual Hispanic	4.56
HH Size 4 Spanish Dominant Hispanic	1.9
HH Size 4 Non-Hispanic	22.8
	100